

Antibiotic Prescribing Patterns in Primary Healthcare Centers in Saudi Arabia: A Comparative Analysis with Global Trends

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Antibiotic prescribing, Primary healthcare, Saudi Arabia, Antimicrobial stewardship, AWaRe classification, WHO/INRUD indicators.

Abstract

Background: Antibiotic prescribing patterns in primary healthcare centers (PHCs) significantly influence antimicrobial resistance (AMR) development. The Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (KSA) implemented a nationwide antibiotic restriction policy in April 2018 to regulate antibiotic dispensing. Understanding prescribing patterns in Saudi PHCs compared to international benchmarks is essential for evaluating policy effectiveness and guiding stewardship initiatives.

Objectives: This review aims to describe antibiotic prescribing patterns in Saudi Arabian PHCs, compare them with WHO standards and international data, and evaluate the impact of the 2018 antibiotic restriction policy on prescribing practices.

Methods: A comprehensive review of published literature was conducted using data from studies examining antibiotic prescribing in Saudi PHCs and international comparative studies. WHO/INRUD prescribing indicators and the AWaRe classification system were used as standard benchmarks for comparison. Data sources included PubMed, PMC, and WHO databases covering the period 2017-2025.

Results: In Saudi PHCs, antibiotic prescribing rates for upper respiratory tract infections (URTIs) range from 24.4% to 44.3% [1,2], with pediatric prescribing at approximately 12.34% following the 2018 restriction policy [3]. The most prescribed antibiotics are amoxicillin (58.6%), Augmentin (28.6%), and macrolides [1]. Watch-group antibiotics account for 51.1-67.3% of prescriptions [4,5], exceeding WHO recommendations. Globally, primary care antibiotic prescribing averages 42.1% (95% CI: 39.2-45.1%) [6], with higher rates in low-income countries (49.1-54.0%) [6,7] and lower rates in Europe (15.2%) [8]. The 2018 Saudi restriction policy resulted in a 23.2-31% reduction in antibiotic consumption [9,10]. After COVID19 it's noticed that there is a substantial increase in the group of Azithromycin and Mix of Amoxicillin and Clavulnic Acid, while on the other hand a reduced rates of

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prescribing for amoxicillin and clarithromycin antibiotics groups compared to pre-COVID19.

Conclusion: Antibiotic prescribing in Saudi PHCs remains above WHO optimal standards but has decreased following policy interventions. The predominance of Watch-group antibiotics and suboptimal guideline adherence indicate continued need for antimicrobial stewardship programs. Saudi Arabia's prescribing patterns align more closely with Middle Eastern and North African trends than with European benchmarks, highlighting the need for region-specific interventions.

1. Introduction

Antibiotic prescribing in primary healthcare centers (PHCs) represents a critical determinant of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) development worldwide. The World Health Organization (WHO) estimates that 20-50% prescribed antibiotics are inappropriate, contributing to the global burden of AMR which was associated with 4.95 million deaths in 2019[11]. Primary care settings account for most of the outpatient antibiotic use, making them essential targets for stewardship interventions [6].

The Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (KSA) faces significant challenges with antibiotic overuse. Prior to 2018, antibiotics were accessible over the counter, with 78% of pharmacies dispensing antibiotics without prescriptions [12]. In April 2018, the Saudi Ministry of Health implemented a nationwide restriction policy prohibiting antibiotic dispensing without valid prescriptions, accompanied by penalties including fines up to 100,000 SAR and license revocation [9,10].

2. Antibiotic Prescribing Patterns in Saudi PHCs

2.1. Prescribing Rates

Studies from Saudi PHCs demonstrate variable prescribing rates depending on clinical conditions. A cross-sectional study in Al-Madinah City reported that 44.3% of physicians prescribed antibiotics for upper respiratory tract infections (URTIs) [1]. However, another study comparing PHCs with emergency departments found lower rates in PHCs (24.4%) versus pediatric emergency departments (46.3%) for URTI cases [2]. A recent pharmacoepidemiological study following the 2018 restriction policy found that only 12.34% of pediatric visits to family medicine clinics included antibiotic prescriptions [3], suggesting policy effectiveness.

The WHO/INRUD indicator for antibiotic prescribing recommends that 20.0-26.8% of encounters should include antibiotics [13]. Saudi PHC data show mixed compliance with these standards, with some settings meeting guidelines while others exceed them [14].

2.2. Antibiotic Classes Prescribed

The most frequently prescribed antibiotics in Saudi PHCs include amoxicillin (58.6%), amoxicillin-clavulanic acid (Augmentin) (28.6%), macrolides, and nitroimidazoles [1,3]. A study at 24 primary healthcare centers found that Watch-group antibiotics (second-generation cephalosporins and macrolides) accounted for 51.1% of prescriptions by number and 52.2% by

defined daily doses (DDDs) [4]. Pediatric patients received Watch-group antibiotics at even higher rates (66.7%) compared to adults (42.9%) [4].

Notably, a post-policy study observed a shift toward narrower-spectrum prescribing, with penicillins (36.90%) and nitroimidazoles (39.29%) predominating, and complete absence of cephalosporins, sulfonamides, and tetracyclines in pediatric prescriptions [3]. This contrasts with pre-policy patterns where cephalosporins represented 28-33% of prescriptions [5,15].

2.3. Guideline Adherence

Overall adherence to clinical prescribing guidelines in Saudi PHCs varies significantly. One study reported overall adherence of only 49.5%, with better compliance for adults (64%) than children (27.2%) [4]. Dental clinics demonstrated better adherence than general practice clinics [4]. Factors associated with higher Watch-group antibiotic prescribing pediatric patients (aOR 2.89, 95% CI: 1.46-5.78), acute respiratory tract infections (aOR 2.62, 95% CI: 1.03-6.69), and urinary tract infections (aOR 4.69, 95% CI: 2.09-10.56) [4].

3. International Comparison

3.1. Global Primary Care Prescribing

A systematic review and meta-analysis of 174 studies from 51 countries estimated the global pooled prevalence of antibiotic prescribing in primary care at 42.1% (95% CI: 39.2-45.1%) [6]. Significant regional variations exist, with the highest rates in sub-Saharan Africa (51.5%, 95% CI: 43.5-59.4%) and South Asia (54.0%, 95% CI: 48.7-59.2%), and the lowest in Europe and Central Asia (15.2%, 95% CI: 14.4-16.0%) [6,8]. The prevalence of inappropriate antibiotic prescriptions globally was 57.6% (95% CI: 43.4-71.2%) [6].

3.2. Middle East and North Africa (MENA) Region

Saudi Arabia's prescribing patterns align with broader MENA regional trends. Point prevalence surveys across MENA hospitals show antibiotic use rates ranging from 39.2% in Tunisia to 93.7% in Iraq [15]. The most prescribed antibiotics across the region are third-generation cephalosporins (Watch group) and penicillins (Access group) [15]. Inappropriate prescribing remains prevalent throughout the Gulf region, with studies indicating a need for improved guidelines and physician education [16].

3.3. European Comparisons

European countries demonstrate significantly lower antibiotic prescribing rates. Data from the European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC) show that the UK's primary care prescribing volume fell from 20 DDDs per 1,000 inhabitants per day in 2013 to 18 in 2019 [17]. The Netherlands, Sweden, Canada, and Finland report the lowest prescribing rates, while Greece, France, Spain, and Ireland have higher rates within Europe [17]. Saudi PHC prescribing rates exceed European benchmarks but are comparable to other MENA countries.

4. Impact of Saudi Restriction Policy (2018)

The 2018 antibiotic restriction policy has demonstrated measurable impact on prescribing patterns. Time series analysis comparing pre-policy (2016-2018) and post-policy (2018-2020) periods showed significant reductions in total antibiotic consumption (mean reduction of -96.9 DDDdq, p=0.002) and oral antibiotic use (mean reduction of -98 DDDdq, p=0.002) [9]. Forecasting models indicated that actual consumption was 30-31% lower than projected values without the policy [9].

Retail antimicrobial sales data revealed a 23.2% overall reduction, decreasing from 818.9 million SAR in 2017 to 648.4 million SAR in 2019[10]. Amoxicillin sales dropped by 70%, though amoxicillin-clavulanic acid sales increased [10]. The policy reduced dispensing without prescriptions from 78% to approximately 12.9% of pharmacies [12].

5. Results

The table 1 shows 8 groups of Antibiotics and shows the number on antibiotics dispensed per drug during the last quarter of 2019. Data suggests that Penicillin Group is the most frequently dispensed antibiotic class, Macrolides were the second most commonly dispensed antibiotics followed by Cephalosporin Group and Tetracycline and the classes had the lowest dispensing rates are Sulfa, Nitroimidazole and Nitrofurantoin.

The table 2 shows 8 groups of Antibiotics and shows the number on antibiotics dispensed per drug during the last quarter of 2025. Data suggests that Penicillin Group is the most frequently dispensed antibiotic class, Macrolides were the second most commonly dispensed antibiotics followed by Cephalosporin Group and Tetracycline and the classes had the lowest dispensing rates are Sulfa, Nitroimidazole and Nitrofurantoin.

Table 1: Antibiotic Dispensing Data for Oct-Dec, 2019

No.	Antibiotic Class	Antibiotic Name	Oct-19	Nov-19	Dec-19	Total	
1	Penicillin Group	Augmentin Tablet	776	960	1024	2760	
2		Augmentin Suspension	760	880	733	2373	
3		Amoxicillin Capsules	650	475	497	1622	
4		Amoxicillin Suspension	141	64	223	428	
						Total	7183
5	Cephalosporin Group	Cefuroxime 500mg Tablet	250	90	217	557	
6		Cefprozil 250mg suspension	24	59	76	159	
						Total	716
8	Macrolide Group	Azithromycin 250mg Capsules	330	107	122	559	
9		Azithromycin 40mg /ml Suspension	340	520	120	980	
10		Clarithromycin 500mg Tablet	144	274	320	738	
11		Clarithromycin 125mg/5ml Suspension	75	100	115	290	
						Total	2567
12	Sulfa Group	Cotrimoxazole Tablet	70	25	30	125	
13		Cotrimoxazole Suspension	10	15	23	48	
						Total	173
14	Tetracycline	Doxycyclin 100mg Capsules	250	250	200	700	
						Total	700
15	Nitrofurantoin	Nitrofurantoin 50mg Capsules	115	50	24	189	
16	Nitroimidazole	Metronidazole 500mg Tablet	54	32	26	112	
17		Metronidazole 125mg Suspension	18	23	26	67	
18	Fluroquinolone	Ciprofloxacin 250mg Tablet	80	260	50	390	

Table 2: Antibiotic Dispensing Data for Oct-Dec, 2025

No.	Antibiotic Class	Antibiotic Name	Oct-25	Nov-25	Dec-25	Total
1	Penicillin Group	Augmentin Tablet	1573	5824	1633	9030
2		Augmentin Suspension	1735	2448	2216	6399
3		Amoxicillin Capsules	154	235	210	599

4		Amoxicillin Suspension	210	325	242	777
					Total	16805
5	Cephalosporin Group	Cefuroxime 500mg Tablet	84	120	240	444
6		Cefprozil 250mg suspension	65	86	77	228
					Total	672
8	Macrolide Group	Azithromycin 250mg Capsules	1340	1768	1666	4774
9		Azithromycin 40mg /ml Suspension	910	358	150	1418
10		Clarithromycin 500mg Tablet	73	121	84	278
11		Clarithromycin 125mg/5ml Suspension	40	60	35	135
					Total	6605
12	Sulfa Group	Cotrimoxazole Tablet	40	45	30	115
13		Cotrimoxazole Suspension	15	34	20	69
					Total	184
14	Tetracycline	Doxycyclin 100mg Capsules	132	200	184	516
					Total	
15	Nitrofurantoin	Nitrofurantoin 50mg Capsules	96	84	61	241
16	Nitroimidazole	Metronidazole 500mg Tablet	100	195	175	470
17		Metronidazole 125mg Suspension	20	55	30	105
18	Fluroquinolone	Ciprofloxacin 250mg Tablet	135	280	109	524

Figure 1: Total Antibiotic Dispensing by Group (Oct-Dec 2019)

Figure 3: Total Antibiotic Dispensing by Group (Oct-Dec 2025)

Figure 2: Total Antibiotic Dispensing by Group (Oct-Dec 2019)

Figure 4: Total Antibiotic Dispensing by Group (Oct-Dec 2025)

The bar graph (Figure 1) shows that Penicillin remains the antibiotic class dispensed, followed by Macrolides, while Sulfa and Nitrofurans are least dispensed.

As shown in Figure 2, still Penicillin Group has the largest percentage of dispensed in 2019. Followed by macrolides, while other antibiotic classes are used more selectively.

The bar graph (Figure 3) shows that Penicillin remains the antibiotic class dispensed, followed by Macrolides, while Sulfa and Nitrofurans are least dispensed group in 2025.

Figure 4 shown in the pie graph that still in last quarter of 2025, Penicillin Group still has the largest percentage of dispensed, followed by Macrolide and same in 2019 other groups are used more selectively.

6. Discussion

Antibiotic prescribing in Saudi PHCs reflects a complex interplay of clinical, cultural, and systemic factors. While the 2018 restriction policy has achieved measurable reductions in antibiotic consumption, prescribing rates remain above WHO optimal standards and European benchmarks. The predominance of Watch-group antibiotics, particularly for pediatric patients, indicates continued need for antimicrobial stewardship interventions.

Comparative analysis reveals that Saudi prescribing patterns align more closely with MENA regional trends than with high-income European countries. This may reflect similarities in disease burden, healthcare infrastructure, and cultural factors influencing patient expectations. Non-clinical factors, including patient requests (52.8%) and perceived pressure (28.5%), continue to influence prescribing decisions [1].

The shift toward narrower-spectrum antibiotics observed in post-policy studies is encouraging, suggesting that regulatory interventions can modify prescriber behavior. However, suboptimal guideline adherence and high rates of Watch-group antibiotic use indicate that policy changes alone are insufficient without concurrent education and stewardship programs.

7. Conclusion

Antibiotic prescribing in Saudi PHCs has decreased following the 2018 restriction policy but remains above WHO optimal standards. The predominance of Watch-group antibiotics and variable guideline adherence highlight the need for comprehensive antimicrobial stewardship programs. Saudi Arabia's prescribing patterns are comparable to other MENA countries but exceed European benchmarks. Future interventions should focus on physician education, guideline implementation, and surveillance systems to monitor prescribing trends and ensure rational antibiotic use.

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